

CONTROLLING ACTUATION AND LOCOMOTION: GEOMETRY-COMPOSITION-HUMIDITY GRADIENT CORRELATIONS FOR SEMI-AUTONOMIC FILMS

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ABSTRACT

Self-organization and synchrony are behaviours demonstrated in living systems, from fireflies to swarming schools of fish and motility of slime mold. In each example, a complex assembly of independent units develops order through the excitation and feedback of relatively rudimentary signals between near neighbors (light, motion, chemical). Synchrony exists in synthetic systems too, such as electrons in an electrochemical potential or an assembly of chemically oscillating particles, suggesting that spontaneous temporal organization could be encouraged through appropriate material design. Here in we will discuss the design of architecture and information transfer of semi-autonomous composites comprised of “active” nodes in an “inactive” matrix. For example, monolithic films of polyimide – sulfonated poly(amic acid) copolymer exhibit oscillatory (~1 Hz) motion, powered by energy harvesting from a vapour gradient. More complex regulated actuation and location can be designed by prescribing sample geometry, and “printing” an absorption rate pattern across the film by local laser anneals to control the conversion ratio of PI-(ester-sulfonyl) to PI-(carboxylic acid). The excellent thermal stability, fatigue behaviour and chemical resistance of polyimides provide materials with outstanding mechanical integrity, demonstrating >100 oscillatory and locomotion cycles without performance degradation. The challenge for such emergent mechanical adaptivity is to understand the interdependent correlation between sample geometry, composite composition, and external energy gradient. Embedding logic and feedback within the component materials and geometry ultimately simplifies system design, reduces sensor demand, and ultimately points toward autonomic material systems (i.e. smart composites) that provide passive regulation within complex environments.

1 INTRODUCTION

Actuation and power-generation mechanisms based on harvesting room-temperature ambient energy of water gradients (i.e. relating to the change in chemical potential) have recently attracted great deal of attention as illustrated by recent reports on actuation and locomotion of poly(pyrrole) (PPy) [1-5]. It has been long known that doped PPy films containing perchlorate counter-ions undergo rapid bending upon asymmetrical water vapour sorption,[1] leading to the design of a PPy motor capable of transducing chemical free energy of water sorption directly into a continuous circular rotation [2]. More recently, a water-responsive polymer composite film based polypyrrole–polyolborate (PPy-POB) spontaneously exchange water with the environment to induce film expansion and contraction, resulting in rapid and continuous locomotion on a wet surface [3]. The film actuator can generate contractile stress up to 27 MPa, lift objects 380 times heavier than itself, and transport cargo 10 times heavier than itself. Similar concepts have been demonstrate for a bioinspired hygromorphic double-layered actuator (HAD) [4] and asymmetric graphene/graphene oxide (G/GO) fibers [5]. Overall, these reported systems are comprised of ionic polymer composites or multi-component materials, making patterning and processing very difficult.

Figure 1 summarizes a non-ionic alternative. Alkylsulfonyl-containing poly(ether-imide) film (~ 3 cm x 3 cm and 30 μm thick) (PEI-SO₂R) exhibits the ability to be self-actuating and locomotive on a wet surface. Briefly, upon being laid flat on a piece of water-wet paper towel, two opposite parts of the film were able to curl up like a pair of wings while standing still, and then moved to another spot by flipping over when the “wings” are in close contact, following by a quick roll-over and flattening action. The self-propelling movement continued across the wet surface until the film arrived at the border between the wet and dry surfaces, where the moving film came to a standstill. Such water-gradient driven locomotion is reminiscent of the PPy-POB composite film reported by Langer et al. PEI-SO₂R however is non-ionic. Also, similarly fabricated film from the unmodified polyether-imide (Ultem) or a hygroscopic polymer, namely Nafion, did not have the same capability under the same testing conditions.

The PEI-SO₂R family provides a novel platform to develop mechanical emergence via active nodes in an inactive matrix. First, these polymers confirm that a monolithic material can exhibit locomotion as opposed to PPy-POB composite films thus eliminating complexities of morphology optimization within one phase. Further, PEI polymers are soluble in common solvents and easily processed, providing latitude in fabrication.

Figure 1. Locomotion of alkylsulfonyl-containing poly(ether-imide) film (~ 3 cm x 3 cm and 30 μm thick) (PEI-SO₂R).

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